

BCG: Limitations and Quest for Future Vaccines

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Abstract- The BCG vaccine, developed between 1906 and 1921, is the sole licensed vaccine against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (*Mtb*). While effective in preventing disseminated tuberculosis in children, its efficacy against pulmonary TB in adults varies. BCG's limitations, including the lack of lasting immunity, highlight the need for more effective vaccines amid the ongoing global tuberculosis (TB) health concern. This paper's main goals are to clarify the BCG vaccine's intrinsic drawbacks and restricted efficacy and investigate other possible vaccinations that are presently undergoing clinical trials. Despite BCG's widespread use, substantial TB burdens persist, urging the development of improved vaccines. BCG's limitations are associated with geographical variables, host genetics, and environmental mycobacteria.

A few potential strategies to increase the efficacy of BCG are different routes of administration, which have been investigated in non-human primates (NHP), murine models, and human trials. Strong, long-lasting protection appears to be induced by mucosal and intravenous BCG administration. Recombinant BCG seeks to improve immunological responses by expressing antigens unique to *Mtb*. Booster strategies, employing adjuvants or revaccination, address BCG's diminishing efficacy. Recent studies support BCG revaccination as a strategy to improve TB control.

In discussing several vaccinations undergoing clinical trials, the report highlights the recombinant BCG variant VPM1002. VPM1002, which is intended to improve MHC-I-related immune responses, has demonstrated safety and efficacy in several animal models. Novel recombinant BCG variations seek to enhance safety and protective efficacy while supporting TB prevention initiatives.

TUBERCULOSIS:

Understanding TB pathology is imperative for designing an efficacious vaccine as well as new medications, and novel therapies. One of the central elements of Tuberculosis pathogenesis is the capability of *Mtb* to sustain in diverse intracellular environments. *Mtb* interacts with the host immune system by either evading the innate immune response or abiding by the adaptive immune response.^[1]

Despite the availability of a significant sum of anti-tuberculosis medications and drugs over the past 50-60 years, *Mtb* persists to be one of the top ten causes of death worldwide. An estimated 10.6 million people fell ill with TB worldwide in 2022, an increase from 10.3 million in 2021. Similarly, the TB incidence rate is estimated to have increased by 3.6% between 2020 and 2021, following declines of about 2% per year for most of the past 2 decades. An estimation by WHO predicts that about one-quarter of the global population has been infected by *Mtb* and stands at risk of developing active TB.^[2] Studies show that about 80% of the lifetime risk of advancement to the disease can occur up to the first 3 years after infection.^[3] Reasons for TB resurgence are complicated and involve the emergence and widespread presence of drug-resistant strains, poor detection rates, public health care constraints, latent infection, and population movements.^[4] To address these challenges, we require innovative interventions, such as shorter, less toxic treatments, improved diagnostics, and more effective vaccines. TB vaccination is not only the utmost cost-effective method for regulating the disease but also allows TB outbreaks to be controlled at the origin and acts as a crucial component for developing novel strategies to eliminate TB's global burden.^[5] BCG is the most widely administered vaccine for tuberculosis globally, with 89% of the world's population receiving it in 2019. But despite its widespread use, there is still a significant global burden of TB, highlighting the need for more effective TB vaccines.^[6]

Bacille Calmette- Guerin (BCG)

The *Bacille Calmette-Guerin* (BCG) vaccine is the only available vaccine among numerous attempts to develop an effective vaccine against *M. tuberculosis*. Physician Albert Calmette and veterinarian Calmette Guérin developed *Bacille Billie Calmette-Guérin*, later termed *Bacille-Calmette Guérin* (in short BCG) between 1906 and 1921 after passing *Mycobacterium Tuberculosis* (*M.bovis*) 220 times until an attenuated strain of *M.bovis* was obtained. *M.bovis* is a causative agent of cattle TB used against human TB by Calmette and Guérin using Jenner's strategy and following Pasteur's strategy bacteria were cultured under attenuating conditions^[7,8]. The resulting strain was found innocuous for a variety of animal species that are naturally susceptible to *M.bovis*. Then the experiments were expanded to field experiments which showed that the vaccines given to newly born calves could reduce bovine TB even at the farms

where the disease was rampant.^[9] Hence, ultimately after multiple experiments and trials, BCG is the only licensed vaccine available for TB which was first used as a vaccine for TB control in humans in 1921.^[10] Since then, BCG is one of the most extensively used vaccines all over the world, BCG vaccine was primarily targeted at infants and young children to reduce childhood mortality against TB infection, especially in the prevention of severe TB diseases such as tuberculosis meningitis (TBM) and disseminated tuberculosis.^[11] Although, BCG can effectively protect infants and young children the efficacy of BCG is highly variable in adults and its estimated protection against adult pulmonary TB ranges from 0-80% based on massive well-controlled field trials. There is no satisfactory evidence that BCG can provide protection more than 10 years after vaccination.^[12,13,14] To develop immunity to Mtb it requires CD4+ and CD8+ T cells producing type I effector cytokines such as IFN- γ and TNF- α and their recruitment to the lung. The inadequacy of BCG's ability to offer satisfactory defense against tuberculosis could be connected to the insufficient elicitation of CD8+ T-cell responses and CD4+ central memory T(T_{CM}) cell response, crucial for establishing enduring immunity against mycobacterium tuberculosis.^[15,16,17,18,19,20,21] It has been suggested that the enduring shield against tuberculosis isn't effectively conferred by BCG, as the rate of Tb rises during early childhood. Moreover, certain investigations have indicated a diminishing safeguard after a span of 10 to 15 years.^[22,23] Thus, the development of a more effective vaccine is indispensable to compensate for the limitation of the BCG vaccine.^[10]

HOST RESPONSE:

The body's defense against tuberculosis requires both innate and adaptive immunity. Macrophages, dendritic cells, neutrophils, and natural killer (NK) cells are among the key cells that identify and eliminate Mycobacterium tuberculosis.^[24] Macrophages and dendritic cells use pattern recognition receptors such as Toll-like receptors and NOD-like receptors to recognize and destroy the bacteria. NK cells, on the other hand, produce cytokines, chemokines, and perforin, and possess an innate memory capacity that is vital for developing therapies and vaccines.^[10]

The adaptive immune response involves both cellular and humoral immunity, with CD4+ T cells being critical for protective immunity against TB. Th1 cells are essential for controlling the disease by secreting interferon-gamma (IFN- γ) and activating macrophages. CD8+ T cells also play a significant role in protective immune responses by recognizing antigens presented by MHC Class I and releasing cytokines, causing cytotoxicity, and inducing direct microbicidal activity. B cells, which were previously thought to have a minor role, have been found to play a crucial part in TB defense by secreting antibodies that boost both cellular and humoral immunity. In addition to these conventional cells, nontraditional T cells like mucosal-associated invariant T (MAIT) cells and CD1+ T cells are also essential for TB vaccine-induced immunity.^[25]

The immune responses triggered by BCG vaccination are not yet completely understood, but they involve both adaptive and innate immunity. The BCG vaccine is given intradermally, which triggers an immune response started off by resident epidermal neutrophils, macrophages, and dendritic cells (DCs). The interaction between host immune system and BCG begins with pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) on BCG and pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) on immune cells.^[26] PAMPs include numerous mycobacterial proteins and cell wall components, while PRRs include CD11b, CD18, TLRs, mannose receptors, and others.^[27] 2 weeks post-vaccination the live BCG numbers peak, which suggests the timeline for the initial innate immune response.^[28]

Innate responses involve the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen intermediates (RNI) by neutrophils, and the secretion of chemokines and cytokines, such as IL-6, TNF- α , and IL-1 α , by monocytes, neutrophils, and other innate cells.^[29] Macrophages play a crucial role as phagocytes and antigen-presenting cells, and BCG-induced macrophage activation has a significant impact on anti-mycobacterial immune responses.

Adaptive immunity involves CD4+ and CD8+ T cells (*figure-1*), with BCG vaccination inducing polyfunctional and IL-17+ CD4+ T cells, which may be considered as potential correlates of protection against TB.^[30] BCG also affects immune-regulatory mechanisms, increasing regulatory T cell (Treg) frequencies and IL-10 production, which can dampen protective pro-inflammatory responses but may also indicate a balanced immune response protective in chronic TB disease.

FIGURE 1 - illustrates the immune response triggered following BCG vaccination in newborns. First, when neutrophils and macrophages recognize BCG at the injection site, cutaneous dendritic cells are activated and move to the draining lymph nodes. Secondly, this triggers the activation of adaptive immune cells. Thirdly, the activation of CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ T cells that are specific to Mycobacteria and have a TH1 profile, which increases the release of granzymes and IFN- γ . Last but not least, B cell activation leads to the development of memory and plasma cells as well as the generation of antibodies that are specific to BCG antigens. Memory T and B cells become resident in lymph nodes after activation.

BCG'S Limited Effectiveness-

Prior to the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, tuberculosis (TB) held the unfortunate distinction of being the foremost cause of death resulting from a single infectious agent.^[2] This position remained unaltered even with the presence of the *Bacillus Calmette–Guérin* (BCG) vaccine. While BCG offers protection against disseminated TB in young children, its effectiveness in combating pulmonary TB, especially among adults, exhibits significant variability^[31,32,33,34]. Of the overall annual TB cases, roughly 90% affect adults, with a higher incidence among males than females.^[2] BCG represents an attenuated variant of *Mycobacterium bovis*. This diminished virulence results from the removal of the RD-1 locus, which contains nine genes, including those encoding a 10kDa culture-filtered protein known as CFP-10 and a 6kDa early-secreted antigen termed ESAT-6^[35]. These proteins serve as essential virulence factors contributing to the pathogenesis of *M.tb*, rendering them promising targets for vaccination purposes^[36]. ESAT-6 has been observed to inhibit TLR2 on the surface of macrophages, while the CFP-10/ESAT-6 complex can suppress the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS)^[37,38]. Moreover, the CFP-10/ESAT-6 complex can disintegrate under acidic conditions, releasing ESAT-6 to destabilize and rupture liposomes^[39]. Since *Mycobacterium bovis* in the BCG vaccine does not express CFP-10 and ESAT-6, it is unable to counteract its elimination by host cells, thus enabling efficient eradication of *M.tb*. This pathogen destruction makes *M.tb* antigens accessible, subsequently triggering the activation of CD4 and CD8 cells via antigen-presenting cells, ultimately leading to the production of IFN- γ , a crucial cytokine in the immune response against *M.tb*^[40].

Numerous hypotheses have surfaced to elucidate the shortcomings of BCG vaccination. These encompass factors such as climatic variables, geographical latitude, host genetic makeup, and the specific BCG strain employed^[41,42,43]. In regions characterized by a prevalence of environmental mycobacteria, particularly tropical areas, prior exposure to these microorganisms can undermine the effectiveness of BCG vaccination^[42]. To expound upon the detrimental consequences of previous sensitization to environmental mycobacteria before BCG immunization, two hypotheses have been advanced.

The masking hypothesis: The masking hypothesis postulates that when the host is exposed to environmental mycobacteria, a certain degree of protective immunity against tuberculosis is conferred, and subsequent immunization with BCG in individuals already pre-exposed does not enhance this protection further (Figure 2). Consequently, BCG, administered to neonates immediately after birth, provides a valuable level of protection since infants have not

undergone prior sensitization, and thus the vaccine's effects are not masked. In contrast, in adults who have been sensitized by environmental mycobacteria, BCG vaccination proves to be ineffective. Therefore, there is a pressing need for a novel vaccine that must exhibit significantly superior efficacy compared to BCG to have a discernible impact on adult populations^[43].

The blocking hypothesis: The blocking hypothesis proposes that prior sensitization with environmental mycobacteria hinders the replication of BCG (Figure 2). This inhibition occurs because a pre-existing immune response to antigens shared by both mycobacteria is present. Replication of BCG is essential for initiating an immune memory response since it is a live vaccine. In this context, a new vaccine must match BCG's efficacy until it is no longer impeded by pre-exposure. To overcome the impact of pre-sensitization and ensure effective protection, a vaccine based on non-mycobacterial vectors such as viruses, recombinant proteins, or naked DNA is required^[44].

FIGURE-2: Conceptual depiction of the blocking and masking hypotheses. In the blocking hypothesis, the effectiveness of BCG (*Bacillus Calmette-Guérin*) in sensitized individuals is diminished as environmental mycobacteria interfere with its replication, suggesting that a high level of immunity induced by these mycobacteria is not necessary. Conversely, the masking hypothesis suggests that pre-sensitization with environmental mycobacteria provides a baseline of pre-existing immunity. Consequently, BCG immunization does not significantly augment protection against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in such pre-sensitized hosts.

The constraints linked to the BCG vaccine underscore the pressing need for the development of new and enhanced vaccine candidates. These vaccines should be both effective and safe, and they must also remain unaffected by pre-sensitization to environmental mycobacteria. Furthermore, there is a crucial need to develop booster vaccines with significant potency, capable of eliciting robust immune responses that can surmount variations in genetic background, ethnicity, and previous mycobacterial exposures among individuals.

POTENTIAL APPROACHES TO ENHANCE BCG EFFECTIVENESS

1. Altered route of administration

WHO has recommended all the TB prevalent countries to immunize Infants as soon after birth as possible with a single intradermal dose of BCG Vaccine.^[45] Routes of BCG delivery to the body are currently given subcutaneously but for better and alternative immunization other methods have been explored like a mucous membrane (Oral, intranasal, aerosol) or intravenously. Numerous studies conducted across various species, including mice and non-human primates, have indicated that administering BCG through lung mucosa delivery proves more effective in defending against aerosol *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (*Mtb*) challenges compared to parenteral BCG delivery. This heightened efficacy may be attributed to the direct impact on the local lung environment.

A. Murine Model

When compared to subcutaneous vaccination, nasal mucosal BCG vaccination in BALB/c mice provides improved protection against pulmonary tuberculosis in the murine model^[46]. Interestingly, BCG administered intraperitoneally enhanced protective splenic immune responses in *Mtb*-infected mice, which continued for ten months after immunization. Upsurged frequencies of CD8+ and CD4+ T cells together with higher levels of IFN- γ , IL-9, IL-11, and IL-21 were the hallmarks of this prolonged response^[45]. Importantly, intranasal and intratracheal administration of the mucosal BCG vaccination was more effective than subcutaneous immunization in inducing the establishment of resident memory T cells and T effector memory in the lungs. The host defense against pulmonary tuberculosis was greatly enhanced by the adoptive transfer of these airway-resident memory T cells, which expressed a PD-1+ KLRG1- cell surface phenotype, into naive animals.^[47,48] Additionally, compared to traditional subcutaneous vaccination, pulmonary mice vaccination administered intratracheally with a greater dose of BCG (107 CFU) offered greater defense against airway challenge with a virulent strain of *Mycobacterium TB*^[49,50]. Therefore, findings from research using marine models strongly imply that administering BCG directly to the respiratory mucosa would end up being a more successful immunization strategy.

B. Non-human primates (NHP)

It is acknowledged that the best models to evaluate vaccine efficacy and identify markers of human immunity to tuberculosis are non-human primates (NHP)^[51]. Furthermore, BCG's erratic efficacy against *Mtb* infection and Tb illness in non-human primates closely resembles that of the drug in people^[52]. Intravenous BCG delivery was found to be more efficient against *Mtb* infection than subcutaneous (SC), intramuscular (IM) or intradermal (ID) methods in early tests conducted on rhesus macaques^[53]. These results have been supported by more research, which emphasizes the potent protection offered by intravenous or mucosal BCG administration in comparison to intradermal immunization's ineffectiveness against aerosol *Mtb* infection non-extremely susceptible rhesus macaques^[54,55]. While the BCG vaccination applied topically provides absolute protection against the extrapulmonary spread of tuberculosis, it is unable to prevent pulmonary tuberculosis (TB), which is linked to increased lung bacterial abundance and more severe formation of granulomas.^[56]

C. Human studies

Human studies were carried out which demonstrated that oral administration of BCG substrain Moreau Rio de Janeiro was well received by healthy adults in Brazil and the UK. It notably enhanced IFN- γ responses specific to PPD and Ag85, building upon prior childhood intradermal BCG immunization, with the effects remaining observable for three months following vaccination^[57]. Also, a limited-scale study investigated the safety and immune response of the Danish strain of BCG through oral and intradermal administration in healthy individuals and found no adverse effects^[58]. It has been suggested that combining the intradermal and oral BCG vaccination regimens will enhance protection against tuberculosis. This is because the vaccinations will simultaneously elicit systemic (blood) and mucosal (BAL) immune responses, respectively^[54]. Aerosolized BCG was initially administered to young adults and children before the late 1960s, and no appreciable negative effects were observed^[55]. Phase I clinical trials have just begun in order to evaluate the safety of BCG delivery via aerosol in healthy persons who have never received BCG.^[56]

Therefore, improving BCG's protection against tuberculosis in humans, non-human primates, and mice by using different methods of intravenous and mucosal immunization has shown a lot of promise. Despite potential technical difficulties and extensive testing in human trials, the results show that the vaccination route selection is critical to obtaining robust and long-lasting protection against tuberculosis.

Recombinant BCG

In addition to altering the vaccination route and revaccination, another actively explored method for enhancing BCG efficacy involves the usage of recombinant BCG. Numerous recombinant BCGs (rBCGs) have been developed and assessed in animal models. We primarily focus on those tested for protection against *Mtb*, which involves modifications to enhance immune responses, such as the insertion of *Mtb* antigen genes, mammalian cytokines, host resistance factors, bacterial toxin-derived adjuvants, and adjustments to bacterial genes to enhance immune activation and antigen presentation. Examination of the genetic distinctions between *Mtb* and BCG has affirmed that BCG substrains lack 16 genomic regions, labeled as RD1–RD16. It is worth noting that certain substrains do retain RD2, RD8, RD14, and RD16. RD1 to RD3 were among the initial regions identified and are found in virulent *Mtb*.^[59] RD1 contains genes for key immunodominant antigens like early secretory antigen target (ESAT-6) and culture filtrate protein-10 (CFP-10), crucial components of the ESX-1 secretion system, which were lost during BCG attenuation^[59,60,61,62]. RD2, deleted only in BCG Pasteur substrains post 1925, carries unique elements like the *mpt64* gene^[61], while RD3, absent in BCG, is found in virulent laboratory strains of *M.bovis* and *Mtb*. This loss of RD1 to RD16 means BCG lacks several *Mtb* antigens, leading to efforts to enhance BCG's TB protection by creating recombinant BCGs expressing *Mtb*-specific antigens, such as ESAT-6^[60,63,64,65]. Additionally, rBCGs overexpressing *Mycobacterium* antigens, such as Ag85B, have

been developed to enhance immune responses. Significantly, the addition of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (*Mtb*) antigens has enhanced the protective effectiveness of mycobacterial strains. For example, removing CFP-10 and ESAT-6 from the MTBVAC strain decreased its protection against *Mtb* in mice to BCG levels^[66]. MTBVAC is an *Mtb* strain that has been attenuated through the deletion of virulence genes *phoP* and *fadD26*.

An rBCG that exhibited overexpression of ESAT-6 resulted in more robust IFN- γ responses that were higher with the modified BCG than with the original BCG, but it did not provide greater protection against aerosol *Mtb* challenge in guinea pigs^[63]. In contrast, rBCG30, which overexpressed the shared immunodominant protein Ag85B, showed significant improvement in protecting against *Mtb* in guinea pig models compared to the standard BCG vaccine^[67]. Ag85B is one of three secreted mycolyltransferases that are closely related and essential for bacterial wall synthesis^[68]. A Phase I clinical trial involved 35 adults who were randomly assigned to receive either rBCG30 or the standard BCG vaccine in a double-blind manner^[69]. The vaccine was well-tolerated, and individuals immunized with rBCG30 exhibited increased expansion and IFN-gamma production in Ag85B-specific CD4+ and CD8+ T cells compared to those immunized with the standard BCG. To enhance the safety of rBCG30 for individuals with compromised immune systems, a new version called rBCG(mbtB30) was developed^[70]. This strain, which relies on mycobactin for iron acquisition, demonstrated improved safety in immunocompromised severe combined immunodeficiency (SCID) mice and exhibited slightly superior protection against *Mtb* in guinea pigs compared to the standard BCG^[70]. Moreover, several other rBCGs expressing *Mtb* antigens, including Ag85A, Ag85B, HspX, and a fusion of MPT64 with the PE domain of PE_PGRS33, provided enhanced protection against *Mtb* in mouse models^[64,71,72].

Booster:

The BCG vaccine administration during infancy safeguards children from widespread and meningeal tuberculosis but its efficacy in averting tuberculosis in adults is comparatively limited^[73,74]. This phenomenon can be explained by the decline in BCG-triggered immunity as individuals age^[75]. One approach that has been undertaken to enhance effectiveness involves the incorporation of adjuvant in combination with BCG. Several illustrations of such adjuvants include clofazimine, lactoferrin, inarigivir, and IL-15^[76,77,78,79,80]. Along with the use of adjuvants, the decline or dampening of immunity can also be overcome by revaccination. Numerous trials involving BCG revaccination have been conducted and the outcomes have varied depending on the specific endpoint examination. In an extensive study conducted by Brazil, approximately 100,000 children aged 7-14 received a second BCG vaccination as a booster dose, while an equivalent number of children in the control group did not receive BCG. The study revealed that the rate of TB occurrence was comparable in both groups, indicating that the revaccination with BCG did not offer any discernible advantage.^[81] However, recent trials and research on BCG revaccination have produced more encouraging findings. In a comparison with the *Mtb* candidate vaccine H4:IC31, BCG revaccination demonstrated a slight advantage in preventing sustained QFT conversion in young adults residing in a TB-endemic area^[82]. Furthermore, BCG revaccination stimulated the production of Ag85A, TB10.4, and BCG-specific IFN- γ + responses along with polyfunctional CD4+ and CD8+ T cell responses, which were on par with or even superior to those induced by *Mtb* candidate vaccines H4:IC31 and H56:IC31^[83]. Additionally, BCG revaccination enhanced IL-22+ CD4+ T cell activity in addition to Th1 cells^[84]. Notably, the research indicated that BCG revaccination enhanced anti-mycobacterial immunity, regardless of prior exposure to *Mtb*, consistent with previous findings^[85]. This aspect holds significance when contemplating the use of BCG revaccination as a strategy in TB-endemic areas.

In summary, recent studies have presented encouraging outcomes from BCG revaccination investigations^[85,86,83] emphasizing its potential as a strategy to improve BCG effectiveness and tuberculosis control, especially in the absence of an alternative TB vaccine candidate in the near term.

VACCINES UNDER TRIALS

There are presently a minimum of 23 vaccine candidates undergoing clinical trials in humans, as detailed in the table. Ongoing advancements primarily emphasize live attenuated, inactivated, subunit, and recombinant vaccine categories. Furthermore, diverse combinations of antigens and adjuvants are undergoing evaluation within the realm of subunit vaccines.

VPM1002

VPM1002 is a recombinant BCG (rBCG) that lacks urease C and expresses listeriolysin derived from *Listeria monocytogenes* (rBCG Δ urec::Hly). BCG and other mycobacteria typically prevent the acidification and maturation of the phagosome once internalized.^[87,88,89] This vaccine has the capability to release LLO, facilitating the transfer of mycobacterial antigens and DNA into the cytosol. This process amplifies the production of antigen-specific CD4+ and CD8+ T cells and triggers autophagy, inflammasome activation, and apoptosis.^[90] Initially, VPM1002 was designed to enhance MHC-I-related immune responses through the cytosolic release of mycobacterial proteins, improving the induction of CD8+ T cells^[91]. Previous investigations have shown that the VPM1002 vaccine can elicit Th1- and Th17-type immune responses, demonstrating greater efficacy and safety compared to BCG in various animal models,

including mice, immune-deficient mice, guinea pigs, rabbits, and non-human primates (NHP).^[90] Furthermore, this particular vaccine has been employed as an immunotherapeutic alternative for patients with non-muscle invasive bladder cancer, serving as a substitute for BCG treatment ^[92]. Several Phase I open-label randomized clinical trials, performed by Vakzine Projekt Management GmbH, were conducted to assess the safety and immunogenicity of VPM1002 in both adults and infants in South Africa (ClinicalTrials.gov Identifier: NCT01113281) and Germany (ClinicalTrials.gov Identifier: NCT00749034). The results showed that VPM1002 can stimulate multifunctional T cells that produce IFN- γ or B cells that produce antibodies ^[93]. This finding is currently being validated in two Phase II clinical trials. One trial, conducted by the Serum Institute of India Pvt. Ltd, focused on infants in South Africa (ClinicalTrials.gov Identifier: NCT02391415) ^[94], while the other trial, led by the Swiss Group for Clinical Cancer Research, is ongoing with adults in Germany (ClinicalTrials.gov Identifier: NCT02371447).

In May 2017, the Serum Institute of India Pvt. Ltd started a phase II/III clinical trial to evaluate the effectiveness of their vaccine against pulmonary TB recurrence in patients (ClinicalTrials.gov Identifier: NCT03152903). However, this trial is not currently recruiting participants. To enhance the protective efficacy or safety of the vaccine, several innovative rBCG Δ ureC::hly+ variants have been developed. These variants aim to boost specific T cell responses or reduce colony forming units (CFUs) and include rBCG Δ ureC::hly_hIL7 or rBCG Δ ureC::hly_hIL18 ^[95], rBCG Δ ureC::hly+ Δ secA2 ^[96], rBCG Δ ureC::hly+ Δ nuoG ^[96], rBCG Δ ureC::hly+Rv2659c-Rv3407-Rv1733c ^[97], and rBCG Δ ureC::hly+ Δ pdx1 ^[98].

Vaccine	Vaccine Type	Phase	NCT Number or Author	Studies
<i>BCG booster vaccines</i>				
<i>MTBVAC</i>	Live attenuate	Phase 3	NCT04975178	<p>Safe in SCID mice and guinea pigs ^[99].</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No adverse effects on development and growth observed in newborn mice ^[100]. • Demonstrates a safety profile comparable to BCG in both infants and adults ^[101] • Shows the ability to improve survival in mice and decrease bacterial burden ^[102], goats ^[103], and nonhuman primates ^[104]. • Elicits greater multifunctional CD4+ T cell responses with a tolerance safety record. ^[105]. • The BCG-prime MTBVAC-boost provides enhanced defense in guinea pigs compared to BCG alone ^[106]. • Intranasal administration of heat-killed M. TBVAC induces robust cellular responses and is humoral both locally and systemically in BCG-primed animals ^[107].
DAR-901	Inactivated	Phase 2a	NCT02712424	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immunogenic and safety, offering enhanced protection in comparison to BCG alone, as observed in BCG-DAR-901-vaccinated mice ^[108] and human adults ^[109,110]
H4:IC31 (AERAS 404)	Subunit/adjuvanted	Phase 2b	NCT02075203	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immunogenic and safe in murine models ^[111] • Demonstrates safety in human adults and HIV-infected individuals ^[112,113] and HIV-infected individuals ^[114]. • Two low-dose regimens efficiently induce polyfunctional CD4+ T cells in normal and healthy adolescents ^[115].
H56:IC31	Subunit/adjuvanted	Phase 2a ongoing; phase 2b recruiting	NCT03512249	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safe and efficiently diminish bacterial load in non-human ^[117,118] and BCG-primed mice ^[116] • Elicit polyfunctional CD4+ T cell responses at a low dose ^[119]. • Trigger immune responses in a robust manner with three doses of H56:IC31 in QFT-negative individuals, while zero additional benefits were observed from the third dose in QFT-positive individuals ^[120].

ID93 + GLA-SE	Subunit/adjuvanted	Phase 2a	NCT02465216	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heterologous BCG-prime ID93/GLA-SE-boost regimen improved survival in the guinea pig model [121,122] and demonstrated efficacy in the mouse model of a virulent Mtb strain [123]. • Induced polyfunctional CD4+ T cells expressing both CD154+ IFN-γ+ or CD154+ TNF-α+ in mice [124] and TB-naïve humans [125]. • The Tuberculin Skin Test remains uncompromised in ID93/GLA-SE vaccinated animals [126].
GaMtbvac	Subunit/adjuvanted	Phase 3	NCT04975737	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The heterologous prime-boost regimen significantly improved antigen-specific responses and decreased bacterial load in comparison to BCG alone and the homologous GaM. tbVac-GaM. tbvac regimen [127]. • Demonstrates efficacy and safety as a heterologous prime-boost regimen in human adults.
Ad5Ag85A	Recombinant live viral vectored	Phase 1 recruiting	NCT02337270	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrates superior efficacy in the heterologous BCG-prime Ad5Ag85A-boost regimen across mice [128], cattle [128], and goats [129]. • Provides a greater degree of protection against TB model of bovine.[130] • When administered intranasally, elicits noteworthy T cell responses in the lung, resulting in enhanced shielding effect with pulmonary challenge [131].
Ad35/AER AS-402	Recombinant live viral vectored	Phase 1 recruiting	NCT01683773]	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elicits a robust CD8+ and CD4+ T-cell response in a manner which is dose-dependent in a murine model [132]. • The heterologous prime-boost regimen significantly induces multifunctional CD8+ T and CD4+ cells [133].
Novel anti TB vaccine				
RUTI	Inactivated	Phase IIb to investigate	NCT04919239	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decrease bacterial load and limit macrophage infiltration within granulomas, stimulate robust IFN-γ release in Th1 immune responses in murine models, and generate a harmonious Th1/Th2 response along with M. tb IgG antibodies which is M.tb antigen-specific [134-137]. • Demonstrates immunogenicity and safety in healthy adults [138]. • Exhibits safety and immunogenicity, even at a minimum vaccine dose, in individuals with latent TB [139].

M. indicus pranii (MIP)	Inactivated	Two phase 3 trials	NCT002 65226; NCT003 41328	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Successfully manage M. tb infection in animal models ^[140,141]. • Unsuccessful in conferring protective benefits when administered as a regimen in human trials with a single-dose ^[142,143]. • Demonstrates good tolerance and immunogenicity and is delivered in both three-dose and five-dose regimens in both healthy ^[144] and HIV-infected individuals ^[145,146].
M72/AS01 E	Subunit/adjuvanted	Phase 2	NCT017 55598 NCT045 56981	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immunogenic and safe in BCG-vaccinated infants and even in healthy HIV-infected individuals ^[147] and M. tb-infected adults ^[148]. • Against reactivated adults with latent TB it provides 54% protection ^[149].
AEC/BCO2	Subunit/adjuvanted	Phase 1 recruitment completed; Phase 2	NCT030 26972; NCT042 39313 NCT052 84812	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced bacterial burden observed in the guinea pig model ^[150]. • Demonstrates dose-dependent potency in stimulating IFN-γ response and effectiveness in both latent and active disease states ^[151].
H1:IC31	Subunit/adjuvanted	Phase 1	NCT010 49282	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrates immunogenicity and safety in murine models ^[152] • Proven safe in human adults ^[153,154] and HIV-infected humans ^[155]. • Two low-dose regimens optimally induce polyfunctional CD4⁺ T cells in healthy adolescents ^[156].
Recombinant BCG strain				
VPM1002	Recombinant mycobacterial	Phase 2 is completed, recruiting for phase 3 phase 2/3	NCT043 51685; NCT031 52903	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrates an acceptable safety profile in SCID mice and animal models ^[157,158]. • Highly effective in reducing bacterial burden and inducing Th1 responses with comparison to BCG-control ^[158-161]. • Effective in preventing TB and proven safe in newborns ^[162].
CysVac2	Recombinant mycobacteria	Preclinical	-----	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrates a continuous reduction in bacterial burden through a heterologous prime-boost approach involving BCG-CysVac2 ^[163]. • Establishes robust immunity both before and after M. Tb exposure, accompanied by the induction of CD4⁺ T cells which are polyfunctional ^[164]. • Elicits Th1 response when CysVac2 is formulated with the Advax adjuvant ^[165].

SapM:TnB CG	Recombinant mycobacteria	Preclinical	-----	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Induces a robust Th1 immune response, leads to a decline in bacterial burden, and enhances long-term survival compared to the parental BCG in mice ^[166].
BCG-Zmp1	Recombinant mycobacteria	Preclinical	-----	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elicits a better immune response against <i>M. tb</i> in comparison to wild-type BCG in mice ^[167]. • Demonstrates immunogenicity and safety in the guinea pig model ^[168].

Challenges in the development of new vaccine candidates:

A single vaccine for TB was developed and licensed more than a hundred years ago which is far less efficacious than the COVID-19 vaccine which was developed within a year after the first identification of the virus in December 2019. According to a particular estimate, it is projected that COVID-19 will result in an additional 1.4 million tuberculosis-related fatalities and 6.3 million instances of active tuberculosis by the year 2025. Consequently, the necessity for enhanced tuberculosis interventions has become more pressing than at any other time, to reach the goal of controlling TB sought to be achieved by 2030 ^[169]. Although 14 TB vaccines have entered the clinical trial stage, still the final protection efficiency of the highly preceded vaccine M72/AS01E is 49.7% after 36 months of research ^[170]. After the accomplishment of the m-RNA vaccine for COVID-19, it is anticipated that a novel vaccine utilizing m-RNA within nanoparticles will be formulated and subjected to testing against tuberculosis in the near future ^[171]. Numerous factors have impeded progress in the quest for an improved TB vaccine candidate, which includes:

- **Lack of Incentives:** The absence of incentives for investment in a disease that predominantly afflicts individuals in low-income developing nations.
- **Biomarker Challenges:** The dearth of dependable biomarkers that could serve as prospective indicators of tuberculosis risk or as markers of protection.
- **Uncertainties in Vaccine Development:** The challenge of addressing the inherent uncertainties associated with the vaccine development process, including the question of whether findings from animal models accurately predict human protection. Additionally, substantial sample sizes are required to demonstrate vaccine efficacy in the advanced stages of tuberculosis vaccine development.
- **Versatility Requirement:** The necessity for a new TB vaccine to be suitable for administration to individuals both prior to exposure, for preventing initial infection, and post-exposure, to prevent disease development. This entails offering therapeutic interventions for bacterial clearance through immunomodulators and the concurrent use of antibiotics.
- **BCG Vaccine Impact:** Since the majority of the population receives the BCG vaccine shortly after birth, and its protective effects wane as individuals reach adulthood, the next-generation vaccine must efficiently safeguard individuals who have already received BCG vaccination.

CONCLUSION

The prevalence of tuberculosis on a global scale underscores the urgent need for more effective vaccines to combat the disease. Although the *Bacille Calmette-Guérin* (BCG) vaccine is widely administered, its limited efficacy, particularly in adults who have been previously exposed to environmental mycobacteria, highlights the necessity for new vaccine candidates. The development of TB vaccines is hindered by several challenges, such as the lack of incentives, the intricate nature of biomarkers, uncertainties in vaccine efficacy, and the variable impact of the BCG vaccine, which illustrates the complexity of using vaccines to address TB. Encouraging prospects for improving the effectiveness of TB vaccines are presented by ongoing clinical trials for various vaccine candidates, including MTBVAC, DAR-901, H4:IC31, and others in which VPM1002 stands out to be the most promising candidate. Nonetheless, it is crucial to conduct extensive research on immune responses against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (*Mtb*) and identify the essential components of these responses, such as their intensity, timing, and migration patterns, in order to develop vaccines that can significantly reduce the global burden of TB. The necessity for innovative and improved TB vaccines is emphasized by the obstacles posed by drug-resistant strains, inadequate detection rates, and the constraints faced by public healthcare systems, as well as population movements. To overcome these obstacles, it is essential to develop vaccines that are both safe and effective and that do not suffer from pre-sensitization to environmental mycobacteria. Furthermore, these vaccines must cater to the various requirements and genetic backgrounds of different populations. The development of effective TB vaccines is vital for controlling the disease and reducing its global impact. The pursuit

of improved vaccines requires ongoing research, innovation, and collaboration. Such efforts hold promise for mitigating the resurgence of TB and alleviating its burden on global health systems and communities worldwide.

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